

Annex to: Scientific opinion on the microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen and defrosting of frozen ungulates meat.
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Annex F – Uncertainty table

Table F.1. Potential sources of uncertainty affecting the different ToRs/AQs and their impact on the conclusions

Source or location of uncertainty	Nature or cause of the uncertainty	Impact of the uncertainty on the conclusions (e.g. over-/underestimation)
Assumptions		
Meat stabilisation post-slaughtering (post-chilling stage)	In this opinion, the stabilisation period is defined as the period needed for the carcass/meat cuts to reach a core temperature of 7°C and to stabilize the pH of meat by chilling applied immediately after slaughter. However, within the scientific literature there are different interpretations of “stabilisation period”, with lack of a clear and universally accepted definition, thus leading to an uncertain variability regarding this factor.	Using a specific definition for “stabilisation period” within this opinion can result in an over- or underestimation of the levels of microorganisms at the beginning of the storage time, leading to an impact on ToRs 1.1, 1.2, 2.2 (in relation to Scenarios 2 and 3 only). However, microbial loads in carcasses after chilling are affected by several other factors, including the initial contamination, chilling conditions, etc. that may have a higher contribution compared to the variable “stabilisation period”. As the same stabilisation is considered in all scenarios assessed, the impact of this uncertainty on scenario comparison is limited.
Coverage of the conditions assessed in terms of changes of temperature, pH and a_w along the storage aerobically and under vacuum-packaging	There is little information about the reasonably representative practices on the storage time and conditions of meat ungulates intended to be frozen, which determine the dynamics of temperature (chilling and storage) as well as the pH and surface a_w of the meat. Two baseline conditions (mean and conservative) have been designed based on data and expert opinion, considering previous EFSA opinion on aged meat (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2023) and in agreement with the mandate requestor.	This lack of information reduces the certainty about the representativity of the range of conditions described as baseline and used to assess the reference and four alternative scenarios. This could affect the outcome of the comparison among scenarios, impacting ToRs 1.1, 1.2, 2.2.

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No inactivation (reduction) of microorganisms during carcass chilling, freezing, storage and defrosting.	Reduction of e.g. <i>Salmonella</i> , ACC and Enterobacteriaceae during carcass chilling (stabilisation) and subsequent storage have been documented. Despite some inactivation may take place during these processes, particularly when the carcass/meat surface dries (undergoes desiccation), the extent cannot be reliably estimated due to knowledge gaps.	Overall, the effect of this assumption leads to an overestimation of the bacterial loads, The impact on carcass chilling is expected to be limited with comparing Scenario 1 (reference scenario) with the alternative scenarios, as all include the same chilling process. Similarly, in the pre-freezing stage the impact is considered to be limited, as refrigerated storage is not considered a lethal condition. These uncertainties mainly impact to ToR 1.1, 1.2 and 2.2. The impact on the comparison of freezing and defrosting scenarios (ToR 2.1 and 2.2) will be limited since the impact is expected to be similar in the defrosting scenarios assessed.
No reduction of microbial loads during trimming/skin removal (for porcine meat) and no cross contamination during the post-chilling stages	Trimming and skin removal can physically remove part of the bacterial load, but the magnitude of effect may vary. On the other hand, re- and cross-contamination between the meat and equipment/personnel in the post-chilling stage during handling and storage of meat was not considered.	While trimming/skin removal may lead to an overestimation of counts, ignoring cross-contamination could lead to an underestimation of the final bacterial levels. The net effect on the initial loads of bacteria is uncertain and impacts on ToRs 1.2 and 2.2. As the assessment includes different initial levels covering the variability of hygienic practices, the impact of this uncertainty is minimal.
The meat surface temperature is assumed to instantaneously adjust to the storage room temperature, which is considered constant with no oscillations	After the stabilization period, the assessed scenarios consist of a constant surface temperature of 3 or 7 °C, with no oscillation as usually happen in cold rooms and trucks due to compressor cycles, defrost cycles, door openings and air circulation patterns.	Oscillations of temperature (temperature hysteresis) with a mean equal to the constant temperature assessed may contribute a higher growth. As the growth rate increases exponentially with the temperature, the wider the oscillation the higher the difference with the constant temperature, particularly at low temperature (Jofré et al., 2019). Thus, the assumption of constant surface temperature underestimates the growth of microorganisms during meat storage, impacting on ToRs 1.1, 1.2 and 2.2. The magnitude of this uncertainty will strongly depend on the

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Magnitude of log ₁₀ increase and log ₁₀ difference (threshold) to consider it microbiological relevant	<p>An increase of 0.5 or 1 log₁₀ unit is generally considered sufficient to define microbiology relevant growth of bacteria and/or differences between the bacterial levels estimated for two scenarios, distinguishing it from the usual experimental variability or methodological counting error and actual increase of microbial populations. When growth is estimated from predictive models, with different levels of predictability and uncertainty, a higher increase threshold could be required to demonstrate a relevant growth potential.</p> <p>For <i>C. botulinum</i>, toxin production has been linked to 2.2 log₁₀ increase according to the predictive model of Koukou et al. (2021). However, this threshold is quite uncertain as the predictive model for toxin production showed an $A_T=1.80$. In fact, from the food safety management perspective, to prevent toxin production, no growth of <i>C. botulinum</i> is accepted.</p>	<p>performance of the refrigeration conditions applied by the food business operators during the storage.</p> <p>The impact of the selected relevant growth threshold on the conclusions (ToR 1.1 and 2.1) is expected to be minimal, in general (except for <i>C. botulinum</i>) as the growth observed for the targeted microorganisms generally exceeds 1 log₁₀ unit.</p>
Extrapolation of the assessment for bovine to equine animals	<p>The size of dressed equine carcasses is similar to bovine and carcasses of both species are de-skinned before chilling. Therefore, temperature decline kinetics was assumed to be similar for the two species. pH decline kinetics and pH_u (see Section 3.2.1 and Annex C) of equine meat do not appear to be different from bovine. There is a lack of reliable data on superficial a_w of equine meat.</p>	<p>This lack of information reduces the certainty about the representativity of the conditions, which could lead to an over or underestimation of bacterial growth in equine meat, impacting all ToRs.</p>
Extrapolation of the assessment for ovine to caprine animals	<p>T, pH and a_w of caprine meat was assumed to be similar for the two species. pH decline kinetics and pH_u of caprine meat do not appear to be significantly different from ovine, although some studies point out to the somewhat higher pH of caprine meat (see Section 3.2.1 and Annex C). There is a lack of reliable data on superficial a_w of caprine meat.</p>	<p>This lack of information reduces the certainty about the representativity of the conditions, which could lead to an over or underestimation of bacterial growth in ovine and caprine meat, impacting all ToRs.</p>

Data

Source or location of uncertainty	Nature or cause of the uncertainty	Impact of the uncertainty on the conclusions (e.g. over-/underestimation)
Time-temperature profiles during chilling	The profiles are based on limited data covering both surface and core temperatures in different ungulates species. This adds uncertainty to the relevance of the scenarios, which might not cover all the existing variation.	The reference scenarios are chosen as to be reasonable but will not cover all cases, and time-temperatures resulting in both less and more growth will occur. Therefore, the assessment can result in an over or underestimation of the magnitude of microbial growth and levels of microorganisms, impacting ToRs 1.1, 1.2, 2.2. Ultimately, the magnitude of this uncertainty will strongly depend on the performance of the defrosting conditions (equipment performance, setting, load, size/shape of carcass or cuts, etc.) implemented by the food bussines operators.
Differences in pH and a_w of lean meat, fat, fascia and skin (porcine meat) and muscles; scarce data for superficial pH and a_w and unclearness of the literature about superficial vs. in-depth measurements	Meat consists of muscle and fat in different ratios, together with connective tissue (e.g. fascia), attached to bones at slaughterhouse level, while additionally pig carcasses usually remain with skin on during chilling. The complex structure of (carcass) meat is usually not addressed in studies investigating pH and a_w , although these parameters might differ for different tissues and muscle groups. Also, the majority of studies do not report exact sampling location for measurements (i.e. surface that is relevant for microbial growth vs deeper that is practically easier for measurement) of the surface of the carcass and meat cuts, making the values reported in the literature not always trustworthy.	This lack of information contributes to uncertainty about parameters reported in studies and may lead to under- or over estimation of microbial growth, impacting ToRs 1.1, 1.2, 2.2.
Changes of a_w and pH along the storage	Values of a_w and pH were assumed to be constant during specific storage phases or throughout the entire storage period, depending on the scenario. The pH of meat is assumed to be constant from the end of stabilisation period, although pH can increase after long aerobic storage period due to proteolysis. Under vacuum-packaging, the growth of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) a slight acidification can be expected. Water activity can increase or decrease during storage (e.g. packaging dependant).	The assumption on constant pH can lead to underestimation (aerobically stored meat) or overestimation (vacuum packaged meat) of microbial growth. The magnitude of the deviation depends on the type of bacteria and most probably limited as the growth rate changes little within the range of variability of the meat pH (See below). The assumption on constant a_w can lead to under- or over estimation of microbial growth, impacting ToRs 1.1, 1.2, 2.2.
Initial concentrations of pathogenic, spoilage and indicator microorganism in meat from	There is high variability of hygienic conditions between slaughterhouses, sampling method (swabbing vs destructive), sampling location on the carcass, animals (e.g. age, cleanliness, origin). However, the high	In ToR1, for pathogenic bacteria, the predicted \log_{10} increase is used as a measure of the bacterial growth potential thereby minimizing the impact of

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different ungulate species before chilling	variability between studies makes the evidence insufficient to establish reliable concentration values for the different indicator microorganisms or pathogens.	uncertainty in the initial microbial concentration on the outputs of the predictive model. For spoilage bacteria and microbial indicators, different levels of initial contamination were used to represent different hygiene levels to account for this uncertainty. Therefore, the impact of this uncertainty has very limited for all ToRs.
Predictive models		
No lag phase for microbial growth, no germination time in spore-formers (e.g. <i>C. botulinum</i>)	Microorganisms were assumed to be adapted to the environmental conditions and physicochemical characteristics of the meat after the stabilisation period, and no cell damage was assumed during freezing and defrosting. Therefore, no lag phase was considered for any relevant microorganism assessed. Likewise, the germination phase for spore-forming bacteria (i.e., <i>Clostridium</i> spp.) was assumed to be negligible and was not explicitly modelled, given its high variability and unpredictability under the studied conditions.	This worst-case scenario, represented by no lag or germination phase can lead to an overestimation of the magnitude of \log_{10} increase during storage and/or defrosting and thus the levels of microorganisms at a given time, impacting all ToRs. However, as results will be expressed in relation to a reference scenario and compared among different microorganisms submitted to similar conditions which will minimise the impact of this assumption.
Input data for predictions	Assumptions regarding environmental factors used as input of the predictive models (e.g., pH and a_w) included the expected average values (Baseline I conditions) as well as the conservative (Baseline II conditions) reflecting conditions highly permissive to bacterial growth and thus leading conservative outputs.	A distribution of pH and a_w values can be expected, the fixed value used as input value for Baseline I conditions (mean), can result in both over- and underestimation of the magnitude of the \log_{10} increase during storage. Baseline II conditions (conservative), results in an overestimation of the magnitude of \log_{10} increase during storage and thus the levels of microorganisms at a given time, impacting all ToRs.
Matrix used to develop and/or calibrate-validate the predictive models	Most models made on meat are generally developed with growth data obtained with the lean portion of meat, which provides higher a_w , nutrients, and favorable physicochemical conditions for microbial growth compared with fat, connective tissues, etc. Water activity values used to predict microbial growth are compatible with the lean portion, but not with fat fraction, which has reduced a_w and nitrogen sources.	The assumption of growth in the lean portion could result in an overestimation with respect to those cases in which microbial contamination and potential growth is produced in the fat fraction, impacting all ToRs. However, the impact of this

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Predictive performance (validation) and calibration of the mathematical models used – Use of data from different ungulate species for calibration (even from species not considered relevant in this opinion)	<p>Similarly, growth rate data used to calibrate/validate predictive models are mostly obtained from challenge test made on lean portion of meat (either grown meat, loin, etc.), not in carcasses.</p> <p>Observed growth rates from the collected experiments were mostly estimated by fitting the primary growth model to data from challenge test (pathogens) or naturally contaminated means (spoilage). Depending on the design of the experiment and the available data the model fitting was more or less robust.</p> <p>In many cases, predicted growth rates had to be obtained by assuming the input value for a_w and/or pH, having a variable impact on the A_f and B_f depending on the microorganisms (see next uncertainties).</p> <p>The effect of aerobic and anaerobic storage conditions is not included explicitly in the predictive models, however a specific correction factor (B_f) could be implemented when the available data regarding the observed growth rate of the microorganisms under these two conditions resulted in different difference between the observations and the predictions (e.g. <i>L. monocytogenes</i> and LAB). However, for vacuum-packaged meat, several scientific articles report no growth at all for <i>L. monocytogenes</i> (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2023). The growth model represents the worst-case scenario.</p> <p>For <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Y. enterocolitica</i> no clear differences between aerobically and vacuum-packaged stored meat were identified, though some studies indicate lower growth potential (N_{max}) in vacuum-packaging conditions (Manu et al., 1993; Nissen et al., 2001).</p>	<p>uncertainty might be relevant when dealing with carcasses but limited for meat pieces and cuts.</p> <p>The uncertainty and correctness of the growth rates captured from literature affect the indexes of performance of predictive models, and when the B_f is used to calibrate the model, it can also affect the subsequent predictions. Under or over estimation of the microbial growth could be expected, impacting all ToRs. The robustness of the predictive models was evaluated (see Section 2.5 and Section 3.3.3). As the predictive models were calibrated when the B_f was not acceptably good, the impact on the predictions could be minimised.</p>
Input values for pH, impact on the predicted growth rate	<p>Meat pH varies within overall reported ranges (as described in Section 3.2.1). However, pH value is not always reported in the scientific studies used to assess the predictive performance of the predictive models, thus it must be assumed to be used as input value.</p> <p>Depending on the assumed value, the growth rate varies depending on the microorganisms. For instance (Figure 2), at 7 °C:</p> <p>For <i>Salmonella</i> (Figure 2A), according to the predictive model of Pin et al. (2011), the growth rate practically does not change within the range of pH of fresh meat. From pH 7 to pH 5, the growth rate decreases by 5%.</p> <p>For LAB (Figure 2B), according to the calibrated predictive model of Mejlholm and Dalgaard (2009 and 2013), little change of the growth rate</p>	<p>Within the range of meat pH, the impact on the growth rate of the microorganisms of interest is minimal for most of the microorganisms considered, except for non-proteolytic <i>C. botulinum</i>. Therefore, the impact of this uncertainty on all ToRs is minimal.</p>

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	<p>is predicted within the range of pH of fresh meat. From pH 7 to pH 5.6, the growth rate decreases by 4%</p> <p>For <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> (Figure 2B), according to the calibrated predictive model of Mejlholm and Dalgaard (2009, 2013), a slightly higher impact can be expected. Changing from pH 7 to pH 6, the growth rate decreases by 9%, while to pH 5.6 by 23%.</p> <p>For <i>Clostridium botulinum</i> (Figure 2C), the impact of pH within the range of pH of fresh meat is more evident. Changing from pH 7 to pH 6, the growth rate decreases by 25%, while to pH 5.5 by 59%.</p> <p>For <i>E. coli</i>, <i>Y. enterocolitica</i>, and <i>Pseudomonas</i> the pH is not a relevant factor included in the predictive model. Therefore, for modelling purposes, no effect of pH was assumed.</p>	
Input values for a_w on the surface of the carcass and meat cuts and its impact on the predicted growth rate	It is experimentally difficult to measure the a_w of the surface of the carcass and meat cuts, making the values reported in the literature not always trustful. Moreover, the a_w is scarcely reported in the scientific studies used to assess the predictive performance of the predictive models, thus it must be assumed to be used as input value. The a_w has a considerable impact on the growth rate of the microorganisms of interest. For instance, for <i>Salmonella</i> at 7 °C, changing the a_w from 0.98 to 0.997, the μ_{max} increases by a factor of 1.5 according to predictive model of Pin et al. (2011). The output of the evaluation of predictive performance of the model is dependent on the assumed a_w values. For the predictive model of <i>Salmonella</i> : Assuming $a_w = 0.980$, the $B_f = 0.65$ and $A_f = 1.80$, while considering $a_w = 0.997$ the predictive performance is much better: $B_f = 0.95$ and $A_f = 1.49$, indicating that $a_w = 0.997$ would be more representative of fresh meat.	Consequently, the assumed a_w value for fresh meat used as input value of predictive models to assess the predictive performance of the model and determine the calibration factor has a strong impact on the results. Similarly, non-accurate measurement of the a_w of the meat surface can lead to biased prediction, either over or underestimating the microbial growth rate, impacting all ToRs.
Predictive models for T and pH during stabilisation period	Predictive models describing pH and temperature decline kinetics assume homogeneous conditions throughout the carcass or meat cut. In reality, significant spatial heterogeneity exists: temperature declines faster according to the part of carcasses considered, and pH kinetics vary across muscles. These gradients are generally not captured in the models used.	Neglecting spatial heterogeneity may lead to under- or overestimation of microbial growth, depending on the location of contamination, impacting all ToRs.
The impact of competing microbiota on the predicted growth of pathogens	Background microbiota (spoilage and/or indicators) can modulate the growth of pathogens, either reducing or even inhibiting the growth through microbial competition mechanisms. This factor was not included in the predictive models used for the main assessments.	As pointed out in the EFSA opinion on aged meat (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2023), not considering microbial competition in the assessment generally

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Post-freezing initial microbial levels used in predictions	Initial microbial levels used for predictions of post-freezing microbial growth are set to 0 log ₁₀ CFU/cm ² , without taking into account estimated levels reached before freezing for the different scenarios. This implies that stationary phase of microbial growth in the prediction is reached later than it would happen in real conditions.	<p>results in an overestimation of the growth of pathogens, impacting all ToRs.</p> <p>A possible exception is <i>Pseudomonas</i> spp. as some articles report the enhancement of <i>L. monocytogenes</i> growth in presence of pseudomonades. However, others have reported a suppression of <i>L. monocytogenes</i> maximum population density by <i>Pseudomonas</i> at low temperature (4 °C) (Buchanan and Bagi, 1999).</p>
Defrosting times modelling		
Simplification of the Lind (1991) model (e.g. omission of surface mass transfer effect)	The model assumes only conductive heat transfer with convective boundary conditions, but ignores surface mass transfer (condensation, evaporation, frost formation). This simplification is less critical for low-drip products or vacuum-packed meat.	Likely underestimation of defrosting times and overestimation of surface temperature rise in products, resulting in under- or over-estimation of microbial growth during defrosting, impacting on ToRs 2.1 and 2.2. However, being carcass and meat a relatively low-drip product, this uncertainty is expected to have a minimal impact.
Assumption of constant and uniform thermophysical properties	Thermal conductivity, specific heat, and density are treated as average values, while in reality they slightly vary with temperature, phase state (ice vs. water), tissue type (lean vs. fat), and composition (species, muscle type)	May lead to under- or overestimation of defrosting times depending on the relative proportions of lean/fat parts, resulting in a slight under- or over-estimation of microbial growth during defrosting, impacting on ToRs 2.1 and 2.2.
Assumption of constant ambient air conditions (temperature, humidity, air velocity)	In practice, air temperature and relative humidity vary due to equipment cycles, air distribution patterns, and load configuration. Heat transfer coefficient (h) is often variable in time and space.	If h values are lower than assumed, defrosting time will be underestimated; conversely, overestimated h values lead to conservative (longer) defrosting times, resulting in under- or over-estimation of microbial growth during defrosting, impacting on

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Parameterisation of the convective heat transfer coefficient (h)	Two h values were selected for each of the conditions of TOR2 to reflect short (dynamic conditions) and long (static conditions) defrosting periods. h values depend strongly on defrosting technology (still air, forced air, immersion, steam, high-RH) but also on product geometry, and packaging.	ToRs 2.1 and 2.2. The magnitude of this uncertainty will strongly depend on the performance of the defrosting room. Although only two generic h values (static and dynamic) were selected, this introduces both a scenario-representativeness uncertainty and a model-simplification uncertainty, since real h values vary with defrosting technology, geometry and packaging. These choices affect the accuracy of the predicted defrosting times. Using generic h values may thus lead to large uncertainty in defrosting time predictions. This can either over- or underestimate defrosting times, resulting in under- or over-estimation of microbial growth during defrosting, impacting on ToRs 2.1 and 2.2. The magnitude of this uncertainty will strongly depend on the performance of the defrosting room and the size/shape of the carcass or meat being defrosted.
Effect of packaging (vacuum film)	The plastic film introduces an additional thermal resistance between the surrounding air and the meat surface. It is expected that this resistance is minimal, and the convective heat transfer coefficient h may remain unchanged.	Not relevant (h not changed) underestimation of defrosting time, resulting in under-estimation of microbial growth during defrosting, impacting on ToRs 2.1 and 2.2.
Definition of "end of defrosting"	The defrosting period is terminated when the temperature in the core, reach the temperature of -1.5°C .	Differences in definition can shift predicted defrosting times by hours, resulting in under- or over-estimation of microbial growth during defrosting and introducing uncertainty in the comparability of scenarios, impacting on ToRs 2.1 and 2.2. The magnitude of this uncertainty will strongly depend on the implementation of the defrosting program (i.e. setting the end of the proces) by each food business operator.
Estimation of thickness	In TOR 2.1, thickness of pieces of meat were defined for the different scenarios. Irregular cuts or carcasses may not fit this simplification, and the model assumes one-dimensional heat transfer through the thickness, which may introduce minor deviations for atypical geometries.	Wrong approximation of thickness leads to under- or overestimation of defrosting times, with potentially large deviations in irregular shapes, resulting in under- or over-estimation of microbial

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	growth during defrosting, impacting on ToRs 2.1 and 2.2. The magnitude of this uncertainty will strongly depend on the performance of the defrosting room and the size/shape of the carcass or meat being defrosted.

References

- Buchanan, R., & Bagi, L. (1999). Microbial competition: Effect of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* on the growth of *Listeria monocytogenes*. *Food Microbiology*, 16, 523-529. <https://doi.org/10.1006/fmic.1998.0264>
- EFSA BIOHAZ Panel (EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards). (2023). Scientific Opinion on the microbiological safety of aged meat. *EFSA Journal* 2023;21(1):7745, 101 pp. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7745>
- Koukou, I., Mejlholm, O., & Dalgaard, P. (2021). Cardinal parameter growth and growth boundary model for non-proteolytic *Clostridium botulinum* – Effect of eight environmental factors. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 346, 109162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2021.109162>
- Lind, I. (1991). Mathematical modelling of the thawing process. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 14(1), 1-23. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0260-8774\(91\)90051-S](https://doi.org/10.1016/0260-8774(91)90051-S)
- Manu-Tawiah, W., Myers, D. J., Olson, D. G., & Molins, R. A. (1993). Survival and Growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Yersinia enterocolitica* in Pork Chops Packaged under Modified Gas Atmospheres. *Journal of Food Science*, 58(3), 475-479. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.1993.tb04303.x>
- Mejlholm, O., & Dalgaard, P. (2009). Development and Validation of an Extensive Growth and Growth Boundary Model for *Listeria monocytogenes* in Lightly Preserved and Ready-to-Eat Shrimp. *Journal of Food Protection*, 72(10), 2132-2143. <https://doi.org/10.4315/0362-028X-72.10.2132>
- Mejlholm, O., & Dalgaard, P. (2013). Development and validation of an extensive growth and growth boundary model for psychrotolerant *Lactobacillus* spp. in seafood and meat products. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 167(2), 244-260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2013.09.013>
- Nissen, H., Maugesten, T., & Lea, P. (2001). Survival and growth of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7, *Yersinia enterocolitica* and *Salmonella enteritidis* on decontaminated and untreated meat. *Meat Science*, 57(3), 291-298. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0309-1740\(00\)00104-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0309-1740(00)00104-2)
- Pin, C., Avendaño-Perez, G., Cosciani-Cunico, E., Gómez, N., Gounadakis, A., Nychas, G.-J., Skandamis, P., & Barker, G. (2011). Modelling *Salmonella* concentration throughout the pork supply chain by considering growth and survival in fluctuating conditions of temperature, pH and aw. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 145, S96-S102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2010.09.025>